

human**tech**

Human-centred technologies for a safer and greener construction industry

HumanTech was born to address the most important challenges faced by the European construction industry today – making it safer, greener and more efficient.

The cutting-edge, human-centred AI technologies we are developing will transform the sector by increasing the safety and well-being of its workers, enhancing circular practices and improving its productivity.

Solutions **we provide**

From wearables (exoskeletons, cameras, extended reality glasses) for workers' protection and support to robots that can collaborate with humans while contributing to the green transition of the sector.

Smart, unobtrusive workers' protection and support equipment

Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence

A new breed of Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs)

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The **HumanTech** Team

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